

Rhode Island, USA Fall Lepidoptera Survey 2021

Harry Pavulaan [coordinator]
606 Hunton Place NE, Leesburg, VA. 20176
intlepsurvey@gmail.com

ABSTRACT: The first TILS-sponsored survey to document lepidoptera near season's end in Rhode Island was conducted Sept. 18 to Oct. 10. The goal was to document southward migrants as well as northward migrants, and also the presence and abundance of resident late season broods in the Ocean State. Unfortunately, due to the COVID-19 pandemic, participation was dampened, but several participants provided a good window to what was flying.

INTRODUCTION

Near the southern New England coast, cool evenings around the beginning of fall generally signal the start of the Monarch (*Danaus plexippus*) migration westward through Rhode Island and Connecticut, then south to the overwintering grounds in Mexico. While this migration is well documented, several other species have been observed to migrate with them. Past observations by the coordinator in 1983 and 1984 confirmed a steady movement of Question Marks (*Polygonia interrogationis*) along the same route, but in considerably smaller numbers. This movement may be more akin to a localized movement of individuals to more hospitable overwintering conditions, perhaps along the coast southward, rather than a true migration. Reports from nearby Massachusetts indicate a similar movement among Mourning Cloak (*Nymphalis antiopa*) butterflies, but not yet observed in Rhode Island. The Painted Lady (*Vanessa cardui*) and Common Buckeye (*Junonia coenia*) have been anecdotally reported to migrate southward in fall along the Atlantic coast but this has not yet been studied in detail. Observations indicate that these two species do congregate in large numbers along the coast in early fall, but no actual movement has yet been observed in Rhode Island. Likely most of these will perish with the onset of winter.

Rhode Island, as well as the rest of the southern New England coastal region, is known for its comparatively moderated temperate climate, compared to inland areas. Rhode Island winters are often tempered by proximity to the Atlantic Ocean and Narragansett Bay, though extreme cold spells are not uncommon. The progression of spring is delayed by several days or weeks, due to the fact that the ocean remains cold for several months into seasonal warmup. Summers are generally cooler overall than interior New England regions, and afternoon sea breezes are a welcome relief on summer days, often many miles inland. Fall sees the reverse of spring, with frosts and freezes delayed several weeks due to proximity to the ocean, which retains its warmth for several weeks into the fall. This extended mild, frost-free period allows continued migration of northbound migrants such as *Phoebis sennae* (Cloudless Sulphur), *Panoquina ocola* (Ocola Skipper) and *Hylephila phyleus* (Fiery Skipper) annually, as well as infrequent migrants such as *Danaus gilippus* (Queen) and *Dione vanillae* (Gulf Fritillary). It also provides continued safe passage for southbound migrants, among which *Danaus plexippus* (Monarch) is best known for.

The 2021 count, spanning Sept. 18 to Oct. 10, experienced a very mild period, with only a slight, steady decline in daily high temperatures. Nighttime temperatures varied considerably, but remained mild, and well above frost temperatures. The below chart (**Fig. 1**) reflects daily high and low temperatures recorded at Providence during the count period. Rain occurred infrequently during the period, mainly over the latter part of September, but most rains were light and mostly occurred during evening hours.

Fig. 1. High and low temperature chart for Providence, R.I., Sept. 18 – Oct. 10, 2021. Based on <https://weather-forecast.nz/> and www.LocalConditions.com.

SOURCES AND METHODS

Lepidoptera were recorded primarily by cellphone camera or other photographic means. The vast majority of images were of live individuals, some pinned specimens. Reports without images were accepted from reliable sources. Records were submitted either directly to the coordinator (Harry Pavulaan) via email or Facebook Messenger, while others were sourced from internet sources: Butterfliesandmoths.org (BAMONA); iNaturalist, e-Butterfly and the Rhode Island Butterflies and Moths Facebook group. Records are attributed to the list of contributors below. Many contributors to iNaturalist use pseudonyms instead of their real names. Those not identified by real name are listed anonymously under “IN” (iNaturalist):

AH = Aaron Hunt	KL = Kevin Lynch via iNaturalist
AK = Alan Kneidel via iNaturalist	KR = Kimberly Rose
AP = Andrea Petruzzo via iNaturalist	KT = Kyle Testerman via iNaturalist
BC = Brad Cheever via iNaturalist	LS = Laurie Sousa-Andrews
BH = Bridget Holzwarth	MM = Melissa Mowry via iNaturalist
BM = Brian Maynard via iNaturalist	MW = Martin Wencek
BR = Bob Rutkowski via iNaturalist	PH = Pamela Aaronson Hamilton
BS = Betsy Staples	PM = Pat Molloy
CE = Chris Ekholm via iNaturalist	RB = Robin Baranowski via iNaturalist
CO = Selia Colechia via iNaturalist	RE = Kelly Reiss
CS = Clare Stone	RN = Raphaël Nussbaumer via iNaturalist
DG = David Gregg	SC = Sean Cournoyer via iNaturalist
DM = David Mozzoni via eButterfly	SD = Sue Dunn
EG = Emily Goyette via iNaturalist	SF = Steve Forbes
HS = Heather Simmons via iNaturalist	SG = Sandra Gaumont
IN = iNaturalist – anonymous	SW = Susan Wesley via iNaturalist
JA = James Michielini via iNaturalist	TI = Thomas Irvine via BAMONA, iNaturalist
JM = Jeff Maletski	TM = Todd McLeish
JN = Jim Natale via iNaturalist	WJ = Walter Jimenez via iNaturalist
JO = Joe MacIndewar via iNaturalist	WM = Wendy Miller
JT = Julie Triedman via iNaturalist	

RESULTS BY LEPIDOPTERA FAMILY

All butterflies and moths are listed under their respective Lepidopteran FAMILY (i.e. Papilionidae) rather than by superfamily. Butterflies are listed in the sequence given in the Pelham (2008) Catalogue. A comment, indicating residency or migratory status, is provided for butterflies only. Moths' residency status is yet poorly known for the most part. Moths are listed beneath each Family group in alphabetical order. Observations of larvae are listed separately, in alphabetic order by genus, regardless of Lepidopteran family group. All records are by city or town (underlined).

PAPILIONIDAE

***Papilio polyxenes* (Black Swallowtail)** – resident.

South Kingstown: 5 Oct. (IN) **1**

PIERIDAE

***Pieris rapae* (Cabbage White)** – resident.

East Providence: 26 Sept. (PM) **2**

Jamestown: 19 Sept. (DM) **7**; 2 Oct. (IN) **1** – Nectaring on *Raphanus sativus* (Cultivated Radish), and *Aster* sp. (Aster).

Johnston: 7 Oct. (MW) **1**

Little Compton: 19 Sept. (IN) **1**

Narragansett: 25 Sept. (MW, WM) **2**; 3 Oct. (CS, MW) **1**; 6 Oct. (MW) **1** – Nectaring on *Buddleia* sp. violet var. (Butterfly Bush), *Solidago* sp. (Goldenrod).

Newport: 26 Sept. (IN) **1** – Nectaring on *Taraxacum officinale* (Dandelion).

New Shoreham (Block Island): 29 Sept. – 2 Oct. (AH) **2** – Nectaring on *Solidago sempervirens* (Seaside Goldenrod).

North Kingstown: 21 Sept. (CS) **55**; 26 Sept. (CS, MW) **68** – Nectaring on *Capsicum annuum* (Bell Pepper), *Eutrochium purpureum* (Sweet Scented Joe Pye Weed), *Hieracium* sp. (Hawkweed), *Trifolium pratense* (Red Clover).

Providence: 29 Sept. (IN, MW) **2**; 30 Sept. (MW) **1**; 7 Oct. (MW) **3**; 8 Oct. (MW) **1** – Nectaring on *Taraxacum officinale* (Dandelion).

South Kingstown: 19 Sept. (MW) **3**; 26 Sept. (SG, WM) **7**; 29 Sept. (CS) **1**; 30 Sept. (CS) **1**; 3 Oct. (MW) **1**; 10 Oct. (JT) **1**

Westerly: 26 Sept. (SG, WM) **5**; 1 Oct. (SF) **1** – Nectaring on *Buddleia* sp. red var. (Butterfly Bush).

***Colias eurytheme* (Orange Sulphur)** – resident.

Bristol: 18 Sept. (TI) **2**

Cumberland: 1 Oct. (MW) **1** – Nectaring on *Aster* sp. (Aster), *Trifolium pratense* (Red Clover).

Jamestown: 18 Sept. (KR, SD) **2**; 19 Sept. (DM) **1** – Nectaring on *Trifolium pratense* (Red Clover), *Aster* sp. (Aster), and *Solidago* sp. (Goldenrod).

North Kingstown: 21 Sept. (CS) **2**; 26 Sept. (CS, MW) **1**

Westerly: 26 Sept. (SG, WM) **8**

***Colias philodice* (Clouded Sulphur)** – resident.

Cumberland: 1 Oct. (MW) **7**; 2 Oct. (MW) **8** – Nectaring on *Aster* sp. (Aster), *Trifolium pratense* (Red Clover).

Jamestown: 19 Sept. (DM) **1** – Nectaring on *Aster* sp. (Aster).

Narragansett: 25 Sept. (MW, WM) **2** – Nectaring on *Buddleia* sp. (Butterfly Bush), *Solidago* sp. (Goldenrod).

North Kingstown: 21 Sept. (CS) **2**; 26 Sept. (CS, MW) **6** – Nectaring on *Buddleia* sp. (Butterfly Bush), *Eutrochium purpureum* (Sweet Scented Joe Pye Weed).

Westerly: 26 Sept. (SG, WM) **9**

LYCAENIDAE

***Lycaena phlaeas hypophlaeas* (American Copper)** – resident.

Barrington: 26 Sept. (BS) **1** – Nectaring on *Symphytichum novi-belgii* (New York Aster).

Bristol: 22 Sept. (IN) **1**; 26 Sept. (IN) **1**; 27 Sept. (IN) **1** – Nectaring on *Solidago* sp. (Goldenrod).

Cumberland: 1 Oct. (MW) **1**; 2 Oct. (MW) **2**

East Providence: 26 Sept. (PM) **2**

Jamestown: 19 Sept. (DM) **1** – Nectaring on *Solidago* sp. (Goldenrod).

Middletown: 30 Sept. (BR) **1**

New Shoreham (Block Island): 29 Sept. – 2 Oct. (AH) **2** – Nectaring on *Solidago sempervirens* (Seaside Goldenrod).

North Kingstown: 26 Sept. (CS, MW) **3** – Nectaring on *Solidago* sp. (Goldenrod).

Warwick: 20 Sept. (SD) **1**; 25 Sept. (IN) **1**; 27 Sept. (IN, SD) **2** – Nectaring on *Hylotelephium telephium* (Autumn Joy Sedum), *Symphotrichum novae-angliae* (New England Aster), *Symphotrichum novi-belgii* (New York Aster).

Westerly: 26 Sept. (SG, WM) **1**; 5 Oct. (SF) **1**

***Parrhasius m-album* (White-M Hairstreak)** – resident.

Bristol: 26 Sept. (IN) **1** – Nectaring on *Solidago* sp. (Goldenrod)

***Calycopis cecrops* (Red Banded Hairstreak)** – resident.

Cumberland: 1 Oct. (MW) **3**

South Kingstown: 19 Sept. (MW) **1**; 20 Sept. (DG) **1** – Nectaring on *Solidago* sp. (Goldenrod), *Symphotrichum cordifolium* (Common Blue Wood Aster).

Warwick: 3 Oct. (DM) **1** – Nectaring on *Solidago* sp. (Goldenrod).

***Strymon melinus* (Gray Hairstreak)** – resident.

East Providence: 26 Sept. (PM) **2**

Narragansett: 1 Oct. (IN) **1** – Nectaring on *Solidago* sp. (Goldenrod).

***Cupido comyntas comyntas* (Eastern Tailed Blue)** – resident.

Charlestown: 18 Sept. (RB) **1**

Cumberland: 1 Oct. (MW) **1**; 2 Oct. (MW) **2** – Nectaring on *Aster* sp. (Aster).

Jamestown: 19 Sept. (DM) **1**

South Kingstown: 19 Sept. (MW) **1** – Nectaring on *Buddleia* sp. white var. (Butterfly Bush).

Westerly: 26 Sept. (SG, WM) **2**; 8 Oct. (SF) **1** – Nectaring on *Nipponanthemum nipponicum* (Nippon or Montauk Daisy).

***Celastrina neglecta* (Summer Azure)** – resident.

Cumberland: 1 Oct. (MW) **1**

NYMPHALIDAE

***Danaus plexippus* (Monarch)** – seasonal migrant, mass southbound movement in fall.

Cumberland: 1 Oct. (MW) **3**; 2 Oct. (MW) **6** – Nectaring on *Daucus carota* (Queen Anne's Lace), *Trifolium pratense* (Red Clover).

East Providence: 26 Sept. (PM) **2**

Exeter: 3 Oct. (BH) **2**

Jamestown: 19 Sept. (DM) **3** – Nectaring on *Tanacetum coccineum* pink var. (Painted Daisy).

Johnston: 18 Sept. (CE) **1**; 26 Sept. (PH) **1**

Middletown: 30 Sept. (BR) **1** – Nectaring on *Solidago* sp. (Goldenrod)

Narragansett: 20 Sept. (BS) **2**; 25 Sept. (MW) **1**; 27 Sept. (IN) **1**; 3 Oct. (CS, MW) **21**; 6 Oct. (MW) **1** – Nectaring on *Buddleia* sp. violet var. (Butterfly Bush), *Solidago sempervirens* (Seaside Goldenrod), and other *Solidago* sp. (Goldenrod).

Newport: 29 Sept. (IN) **9** – Nectaring on *Nipponanthemum nipponicum* (Nippon or Montauk Daisy).

New Shoreham (Block Island): 29 Sept. – 2 Oct. (AH) **3** – Nectaring on *Solidago sempervirens* (Seaside Goldenrod).

North Kingstown: 26 Sept. (CS, JA, MW) **13**; 27 Sept. (BC) **1** – Nectaring on *Buddleia* sp. (Butterfly Bush), *Eutrochium purpureum* (Sweet Scented Joe Pye Weed), *Hieracium* sp. (Hawkweed), *Trifolium pratense* (Red Clover).

Pawtucket: 26 Sept. (IN) **1** – Nectaring on *Buddleia* sp. violet var. (Butterfly Bush).

Providence: 27 Sept. (MW) **1** – Nectaring on *Linaria vulgaris* (Butter and Eggs).

South Kingstown: 26 Sept. (CS, MW, SG, WM) **5**; 3 Oct. (MW) **4** – Nectaring on *Buddleia* sp. white var. (Butterfly Bush).

Westerly: 26 Sept. (SG, WM) **7**; 27 Sept. (MM) **1** – Nectaring on *Buddleia* sp. violet var. (Butterfly Bush); 30 Sept. (JM)

100's – Roosting on *Rosa rugosa* (Beach Rose)

***Argynnis cybele* (Great Spangled Fritillary)** – resident.

North Scituate: 21 Sept. (IN) **1**

***Phyciodes tharos tharos* (Pearl Crescent)** – resident.

Cumberland: 2 Oct. (MW) **1** – Nectaring on *Aster* sp. (Aster).

Jamestown: 19 Sept. (DM) **1** – Nectaring on *Coreopsis* sp. (Tickseed).

Johnston: 20 Sept. (TM) **1** – Nectaring on *Aster* sp. (Aster).

***Polygonia interrogationis* (Question Mark)** – resident and evidence of seasonal migration: westbound movement in fall along south shore.

Cumberland: 2 Oct. (MW) **1** – Nectaring on *Aster* sp. (Aster).

Richmond: 25 Sept. (CO) **1**

***Junonia coenia* (Common Buckeye)** – seasonal migrant, perishing with onset of winter, though anecdotal reports along the eastern U. S. coast suggest some migratory activity southward in fall.

New Shoreham (Block Island): 29 Sept. – 2 Oct. (AH) **1** – Nectaring on *Solidago sempervirens* (Seaside Goldenrod).

South Kingstown: 2 Oct. (IN) **1**

Westerly: 26 Sept. (SG, WM) **3**

***Vanessa virginiensis* (American Lady)** – seasonal migrant, perishing with onset of winter.

Bristol: 26 Sept. (IN) **1**

Cumberland: 2 Oct. (MW) **1** – Nectaring on *Aster* sp. (Aster).

Jamestown: 19 Sept. (DM) **2** – Nectaring on *Buddleia* sp. purple var. (Butterfly Bush).

Narragansett: 25 Sept. (WM) **2**; 3 Oct. (CS, MW) **1** – Nectaring on *Buddleia* sp. (Butterfly Bush), *Solidago* sp. (Goldenrod).

North Kingstown: 26 Sept. (CS, MW) **7** – Nectaring on *Buddleia* sp. (Butterfly Bush), *Eutrochium purpureum* (Sweet Scented Joe Pye Weed).

South Kingstown: 26 Sept. (CS, MW, SG, WM) **4** – Nectaring on *Rudbeckia hirta* (Black Eyed Susan), *Zinnia* sp. (Zinnia).

Westerly: 26 Sept. (SG, WM) **2**; 8 Oct. (SF) **1** – Nectaring on *Nipponanthemum nipponicum* (Nippon or Montauk Daisy).

***Vanessa atalanta* (Red Admiral)** – seasonal migrant, perishing with onset of winter.

Charlestown: 27 Sept. (JN) **1**

Jamestown: 19 Sept. (DM) **2**

New Shoreham (Block Island): 9 Oct. (IN) **1** – Nectaring on *Buddleia* sp. purple var. (Butterfly Bush).

Westerly: 8 Oct. (SF) **1** – Nectaring on *Nipponanthemum nipponicum* (Nippon or Montauk Daisy).

HESPERIIDAE

***Atalopedes campestris huron* (Sachem)** – resident.

Bristol: 26 Sept. (IN) **1** – Nectaring on *Verbena bonariensis* (Purpletop Vervain)

Jamestown: 18 Sept. (SD) **1**; 19 Sept. (DM) **4** – Nectaring on *Solidago* sp. (Goldenrod).

Narragansett: 25 Sept. (WM) **6** – Nectaring on *Buddleia* sp. (Butterfly Bush), *Solidago* sp. (Goldenrod).

New Shoreham (Block Island): 29 Sept. – 2 Oct. (AH) ~**50** – Nectaring on *Solidago sempervirens* (Seaside Goldenrod).

North Kingstown: 26 Sept. (CS, MW) **7** – Nectaring on *Buddleia* sp. (Butterfly Bush), *Eutrochium purpureum* (Sweet Scented Joe Pye Weed).

South Kingstown: 19 Sept. (MW) **1**; 26 Sept. (SG, WM) **5** – Nectaring on *Buddleia* sp. violet var. (Butterfly Bush), *Symphotrichum novae-angliae* (New England Aster).

Westerly: 26 Sept. (SG, WM) **10** – Nectaring on *Buddleia* sp. (Butterfly Bush), *Trifolium pratense* (Red Clover).

***Hylephila phyleus phyleus* (Fiery Skipper)** - seasonal migrant, perishing with onset of winter.

North Kingstown: 26 Sept. (CS, MW) **1** – Nectaring on *Buddleia* sp. (Butterfly Bush).

***Polites peckius* (Peck's Skipper)** – resident.

Cumberland: 2 Oct. (MW) **3** – Nectaring on *Trifolium pratense* (Red Clover).

Narragansett: 25 Sept. (WM) **2** – Nectaring on *Buddleia* sp. (Butterfly Bush), *Solidago* sp. (Goldenrod).

***Lon zabulon* (Zabulon Skipper)** – resident.

Cumberland: 2 Oct. (MW) **1** – Nectaring on *Trifolium pratense* (Red Clover).

South Kingstown: 19 Sept. (MW) **1** – Nectaring on *Symphotrichum novae-angliae* (New England Aster).

***Ancyloxypha numitor* (Least Skipper)** – resident.

Warwick: 1 Oct. (DM) **1**

***Panoquina ocola* (Ocola Skipper)** – seasonal migrant, perishing with onset of winter.

Narragansett: 3 Oct. (CS, MW) **1** – Nectaring on *Buddleia* sp. violet var. (Butterfly Bush).

GELECHIIDAE

Chionodes arenella (Arenella Moth)

New Shoreham (Block Island): 30 Sept. – 7 Oct. (AH) 1 – Nectaring on *Solidago sempervirens* (Seaside Goldenrod).

Coelostathma discopunctana (The Batman Moth)

Cumberland: 1 Oct. (DG) 1

TORTRICIDAE

Pelochrista oraria (no common name)

New Shoreham (Block Island): 26 Sept. – 4 Oct. (AH) 3

PYRALIDAE

Phycitodes reliquellum (White-edged Phycitodes)

New Shoreham (Block Island): 30 Sept. – 7 Oct. (AH) 3 – Nectaring on *Solidago sempervirens* (Seaside Goldenrod).

CRAMBIDAE

Agriphila vulgivagellus (Vagabond Crambus)

East Providence: 26 Sept. (IN) 1

Crambus praefectellus (Common Grass-veneer)

East Providence: 26 Sept. (IN) 1

Crambus leachellus (Leach's Grass-veneer)

New Shoreham (Block Island): 30 Sept. – 7 Oct. (AH) 3 – Nectaring on *Solidago sempervirens* (Seaside Goldenrod) and other *Solidago* sp. (Goldenrod).

Diacme adipaloides (Darker Diacme)

New Shoreham (Block Island): 8 Oct. (AH) 1

Duponchelia fovealis (European Pepper Moth)

Bristol: 22 Sept. (TI) 1

Pediasia trisecta (Sod Webworm Moth)

Cumberland: 1 Oct. (DG) 1

East Providence: 26 Sept. (IN) 1

Spoladea recurvalis (Hawaiian Beet Webworm Moth)

Bristol: 18 Sept. (TI) 1

Westerly: 1 Oct. (SF) 1

SATURNIIDAE

Hemileuca maia maia (Coastal Barrens Buckmoth)

Exeter: 3 Oct. (AK) 2

SPHINGIDAE

Hemaris diffinis (Snowberry Clearwing)

Newport: 25 Sept. (KT) 1 – Nectaring on *Buddleia* sp., white var. (Butterfly Bush).

Manduca quinquemaculatus (Five-spotted Hawkmoth)

Westerly: 2 Oct. (SF) 1

GEOMETRIDAE

Costaconvexa centrostrigaria (Bent-line Carpet Moth)

New Shoreham (Block Island): 30 Sept. – 7 Oct. (AH) 1 – Nectaring on *Solidago sempervirens* (Seaside Goldenrod).

***Ennomos magnaria* (Maple Spanworm Moth)**

New Shoreham (Block Island): 8 Oct. (AH) 1

***Eupithecia miserulata* (Common Eupithecia)**

New Shoreham (Block Island): 30 Sept. – 7 Oct. (AH) 3 – Nectaring on *Solidago sempervirens* (Seaside Goldenrod).

***Glenoides texanaria* (Texas Gray Moth)**

Bristol: 28 Sept. (TI) 1

New Shoreham (Block Island): 30 Sept. (AH) 3 – Nectaring on *Solidago* sp. (Goldenrod).

Westerly: 20 Sept. (SF) 1

***Idaea dimidiata* (Single-dotted Wave)**

East Providence: 26 Sept. (IN) 1

***Orthonama obstipata* (The Gem)**

New Shoreham (Block Island): 30 Sept. – 7 Oct. (AH) 2 – Nectaring on *Solidago sempervirens* (Seaside Goldenrod).

***Pleuroprucha insulsaria* (Common Tan Wave)**

East Providence: 18 Sept. (IN) 2

New Shoreham (Block Island): 30 Sept. – 7 Oct. (AH) 15 – Nectaring on *Solidago sempervirens* (Seaside Goldenrod).

***Prochoerodes lineola lineola* (Large Maple Spanworm Moth)**

Westerly: 8 Oct. (SF) 1

EREBIDAE

***Cisseps fulvicollis* (Yellow-collared Scape Moth)**

Cumberland: 1 – 2 Oct. (DG) 1

New Shoreham (Block Island): 29 Sept. – 2 Oct. (AH) 6 – Nectaring on *Solidago sempervirens* (Seaside Goldenrod).

South Kingstown: 9 Oct. (JO) 1

***Caenurgina crassiuscula* (Clover Looper)**

Cumberland: 1 – 2 Oct. (DG) 1

***Hypena scabra* (Green Cloverworm Moth)**

New Shoreham (Block Island): 30 Sept. – 7 Oct. (AH) 1 – Nectaring on *Solidago sempervirens* (Seaside Goldenrod).

***Hypercompe scribonia* (Giant Leopard Moth)**

Cumberland: 1 Oct. (DG) 1

***Idia aemula* (Common Idia)**

Smithfield: 8 Oct. (IN) 1

***Idia americalis* (American Idia)**

Cumberland: 2 Oct. (DG) 1

***Tetanolita mynesalis* (Smoky Tetanolita)**

New Shoreham (Block Island): 8 Oct. (AH) 1

***Zale aeruginosa* (Green-dusted Zale)**

Narragansett: 18 Sept. (IN) 1

NOCTUIDAE

***Abagrotis cupida* (Cupid Dart)**

New Shoreham (Block Island): 30 Sept. – 7 Oct. (AH) 1 – Nectaring on *Solidago sempervirens* (Seaside Goldenrod).

***Agnorisma badinodis* (Pale-banded Dart)**

Barrington: 1 Oct. (RE) 1

New Shoreham (Block Island): 26 Sept. – 8 Oct. (AH) 24 – Nectaring on *Solidago sempervirens* (Seaside Goldenrod) and other *Solidago* sp. (Goldenrod).

***Agrotis gladiaria* (Swordsman Dart)**

New Shoreham (Block Island): 30 Sept. – 7 Oct. (AH) 1 – Nectaring on *Solidago sempervirens* (Seaside Goldenrod).

***Agrotis ipsilon* (Ipsilon Dart)**

Cumberland: 30 Sept. – 2 Oct. (DG) 10

New Shoreham (Block Island): 30 Sept. – 7 Oct. (AH) 4 – Nectaring on *Solidago sempervirens* (Seaside Goldenrod).

***Agrotis venerabilis* (Venerable Dart)**

Cumberland: 2 Oct. (DG) 1

***Agrotis vetusta* (Old Man Dart)**

New Shoreham (Block Island): 30 Sept. – 7 Oct. (AH) 14 – Nectaring on *Solidago sempervirens* (Seaside Goldenrod).

***Anagrapha falcifera* (Celery Looper)**

Cumberland: 1 – 2 Oct. (DG) 1

***Anicla infecta* (Green Cutworm)**

New Shoreham (Block Island): 30 Sept. – 7 Oct. (AH) 1 – Nectaring on *Solidago sempervirens* (Seaside Goldenrod).

***Apamea helva* (Yellow Three-spot Moth)**

Cumberland: 2 Oct. (DG) 1

***Apamea lintneri* (Sand Wainscot)**

New Shoreham (Block Island): 20 Sept. (AH) 1

***Autographa precatationis* (Common Looper)**

Glocester: 7 Oct. (IN) 1

Smithfield: 29 Sept. (IN) 1

Westerly: 1 Oct. (SF) 1 – Nectaring on *Buddleia* sp. violet var. (Butterfly Bush).

***Choephora fungorum* (Bent-line Dart)**

New Shoreham (Block Island): 8 Oct. (AH) 1

***Chrysodeixis includens* (Soybean Looper)**

New Shoreham (Block Island): 29 Sept. – 2 Oct. (AH) 1 – Nectaring on *Solidago sempervirens* (Seaside Goldenrod).

***Euxoa detersa* (Rubbed Dart)**

New Shoreham (Block Island): 19 Sept. – 7 Oct. (AH) 48 – Nectaring on *Solidago sempervirens* (Seaside Goldenrod).

***Feltia herilis* (Master's Dart)**

New Shoreham (Block Island): 30 Sept. – 7 Oct. (AH) 2 – Nectaring on *Solidago sempervirens* (Seaside Goldenrod) and other *Solidago* sp. (Goldenrod).

***Feltia jaculifera* (Dingy Cutworm)**

New Shoreham (Block Island): 30 Sept. – 7 Oct. (AH) 2 – Nectaring on *Solidago sempervirens* (Seaside Goldenrod).

***Feltia subterranea* (Subterranean Dart)**

New Shoreham (Block Island): 30 Sept. – 7 Oct. (AH) 1 – Nectaring on *Solidago sempervirens* (Seaside Goldenrod).

***Galgula partita* (The Wedgeling)**

New Shoreham (Block Island): 30 Sept. – 7 Oct. (AH) 1 – Nectaring on *Solidago sempervirens* (Seaside Goldenrod).

***Helicoverpa zea* (Corn Earworm)**

New Shoreham (Block Island): 29 Sept. – 7 Oct. (AH) 5 – Nectaring on *Solidago sempervirens* (Seaside Goldenrod).

***Lacinipolia renigera* (Bristly Cutworm)**

East Providence: 26 Sept. (IN) 1

New Shoreham (Block Island): 30 Sept. – 7 Oct. (AH) 10 – Nectaring on *Solidago sempervirens* (Seaside Goldenrod) and other *Solidago* sp. (Goldenrod).

***Leucania adjuta* (Adjutant Wainscot)**

New Shoreham (Block Island): 30 Sept. (AH) 1 – Nectaring on *Solidago* sp. (Goldenrod).

***Mythimna unipuncta* (White-Speck Armyworm)**

New Shoreham (Block Island): 30 Sept. – 7 Oct. (AH) 1 – Nectaring on *Solidago sempervirens* (Seaside Goldenrod).

***Noctua pronuba* (Large Yellow Underwing)**

East Providence: 18 Sept. (IN) 1

New Shoreham (Block Island): 30 Sept. – 7 Oct. (AH) 1 – Nectaring on *Solidago sempervirens* (Seaside Goldenrod).

***Papaipema duovata* (Seaside Goldenrod Borer Moth)**

New Shoreham (Block Island): 1 Oct. – 7 Oct. (AH) 14

***Papaipema speciosissima* (Osmunda Borer Moth)**

Westerly: 6 Oct. (SF) 1

***Peridroma saucia* (Pearly Underwing)**

New Shoreham (Block Island): 30 Sept. – 7 Oct. (AH) 1 – Nectaring on *Solidago sempervirens* (Seaside Goldenrod).

***Spodoptera frugiperda* (Fall Armyworm Moth)**

New Shoreham (Block Island): 29 Sept. – 7 Oct. (AH) 49 – Nectaring on *Solidago sempervirens* (Seaside Goldenrod) and other *Solidago* sp. (Goldenrod).

***Spodoptera ornithogalli* (Yellow-striped Armyworm Moth)**

Narragansett: 30 Sept. (IN) 1

New Shoreham (Block Island): 30 Sept. – 8 Oct. (AH) 7 – Nectaring on *Solidago sempervirens* (Seaside Goldenrod).

***Sunira bicolorago* (Bicolored Sallow)**

New Shoreham (Block Island): 30 Sept. – 7 Oct. (AH) 12 – Nectaring on *Solidago sempervirens* (Seaside Goldenrod) and other *Solidago* sp. (Goldenrod).

Smithfield: 1 Oct. (IN) 1; 8 Oct. (IN) 1

***Tricholita signata* (Signate Quaker)**

New Shoreham (Block Island): 30 Sept. – 7 Oct. (AH) 1 – Nectaring on *Solidago sempervirens* (Seaside Goldenrod).

***Xestia smithii* (Smith's Dart)**

New Shoreham (Block Island): 30 Sept. (AH) 1 – Nectaring on *Solidago* sp. (Goldenrod).

LARVAE OBSERVED

BUTTERFLIES (all genera listed in alphabetic order):

***Danaus plexippus* (Monarch)**

Exeter: 22 Sept. (BH) 1 – On *Asclepias incarnata* (Swamp Milkweed).

South Kingstown: 29 Sept. (BM) 1 – On *Asclepias* (= *Gomphocarpus*) *physocarpa* (Balloon Plant).

***Papilio polyxenes* (Black Swallowtail)**

South Kingstown: 28 Sept. (IN) 1 – On *Anethum graveolens* (Dill)

Tiverton: 19 Sept. (EG) 3 – On *Petroselinum crispum* (Parsley)

Westerly: 26 Sept. (SW) 1 – On *Daucus carota* (Carrot)

MOTHS (all genera listed in alphabetic order):

***Acharia stimulea* (Saddleback Caterpillar)**

Charlestown: 24 Sept. (LS) 1; 2 Oct. (HS) 1

***Acrionicta americana* (American Dagger)**

Glocester: 23 Sept. (IN) 1

***Acrionicta oblinata* (Smearred Dagger)**

New Shoreham (Block Island): 30 Sept. (IN) 1

***Agrotis ipsilon* (Black Cutworm)**

Providence: 1 Oct. (WJ) 1

***Arctia caja* (Great Tiger Moth)**

Middletown: 30 Sept. (BR) 1

***Automeris io* (Io Moth)**

Middletown: 22 Sept. (KL) 1

***Cameraria aceriella* (Maple Leafblotch Miner)**

Bristol: 10 Oct. (TI) 1 – Feeding evidence on *Acer rubrum* (Red Maple).

***Cameraria caryaefoliella* (Pecan Leaf Miner)**

Johnston: 18 Sept. (IN) – Feeding evidence on *Carya* sp. (Hickory).

***Cameraria guttifinitella* (Poison Ivy Leaf Miner)**

Johnston: 18 Sept. (IN) – Feeding evidence on *Toxicodendron radicans* (Poison Ivy).

***Chloridea virescens* (Tobacco Budworm)**

South Kingstown: 26 Sept. (SC) 1

***Coptotriche badiella* (White Oak Leaf Miner)**

Johnston: 18 Sept. (IN) 1 – Feeding evidence on *Quercus alba* (White Oak).

***Cameraria corylisella* (Hazel Blotch Miner)**

Johnston: 18 Sept. (IN) 1 – Feeding evidence on *Corylus cornuta* (Beaked Hazel).

***Cameraria hamameliella* (Witch Hazel Leaf Miner)**

Johnston: 18 Sept. (IN) 1 – Feeding evidence on *Hamamelis virginiana* (American Witch Hazel).

***Cucullia convexipennis* (Brown-hooded Owlet)**

South Kingstown: 26 Sept. (SG, WM) 1

***Glaucolepis saccharella* (no common name)**

Bristol: 30 Sept. (TI) 1 – Feeding evidence on *Acer rubrum* (Red Maple).

***Lophocampa caryae* (Hickory Tussock Moth)**

Narragansett: 24 Sept. (RN) 1

***Panthea furcilla* (Eastern Panthea)**

South Kingstown: 26 Sept. (IN) 1 – On *Pinus* sp. (Pine)

***Parectopa robiniella* (Locust Digitate Leaf Miner)**

Bristol: 18 Sept. (IN) 1 – Feeding evidence on *Robinia pseudoacacia* (Black Locust).

***Phosphila turbulenta* (Turbulent Phosphila)**

Bristol: 3 Oct. (IN) 1

South Kingstown: 23 Sept. (AP) 1

***Phyllocnistis liriodendronella* (Tulip Tree Leaf Miner)**

Bristol: 21 Sept. (IN) 1 – Feeding evidence on *Liriodendron tulipifera* (Tulip Tree).

***Phyllocnistis vitifoliella* (Grape Leaf Miner)**

Bristol: 26 Sept. (IN) 1 – On *Vitis cinerea* (Graybark Grape)

***Pyrrharctia isabella* (Woolly Bear Caterpillar)**

Middletown: 22 Sept. (KL) 1

Newport: 6 Oct. (BC) 1

New Shoreham (Block Island): 1 Oct. (AH) 1

Smithfield: 10 Oct. (IN) 1

***Spilosoma virginica* (Virginian Tiger Moth)**

Cumberland: 1 – 2 Oct. (DG) 2

East Providence: 18 Sept. (IN) 1 – On *Salix nigra* (Black Willow)

***Stigmella intermedia* (Intermediate Leafminer)**

Bristol: 9 Oct. (IN) 1 – Feeding evidence.

***Stigmella multispicata* (Asian Elm Leafminer)**

New Shoreham (Block Island): 29 Sept. (AH) 12

***Stigmella rhoifoliella* (no common name)**

Bristol: 18 Sept. (IN) – Feeding evidence on *Toxicodendron radicans* (Poison Ivy).

***Stigmella tiliella* (Basswood Leafminer)**

Bristol: 26 Sept. (TI) 1 – Feeding evidence on *Tilia americana* (American Basswood).

***Stigmella villosella* (no common name)**

Bristol: 3 Oct (IN) 1; 9 Oct. (IN) 1 – Feeding evidence on *Rubus* sp. (Blackberry).

***Thyridopteryx ephemeraeformis* (Evergreen Bagworm Moth)**

Warwick: 29 Sept. (IN) 8 – On *Juniperus virginiana* (Eastern Red Cedar).

PUPA/COCOON OBSERVED

***Hyalophora cecropia* (Cecropia Moth)**

Warwick: 18 Sept. (IN) 1

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